

SPACE GROUP DETERMINATION OF THE CRYSTALS OF MELAMINE.

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The dimensions of the unit cell of the crystal of melamine have been found to be $a = 10.52\text{\AA}$; $b = 7.44\text{\AA}$; $c = 7.33\text{\AA}$. The list of reflecting planes in the crystal shows that the planes (h0l) are halved if h is odd and (0lo) is also halved. These halvings assign the crystal to the space group C_{2h}^2 . The number of molecules in the unit cell is four.

The crystals of a large number of compounds having one or more benzene rings have been thoroughly studied by X-ray methods. But so far the crystalline structure of only a few substances having a heterocyclic ring of carbon and nitrogen has been completely determined (*cf.* Knaggs, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1935, **A** 150, 576; Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1195; Lansdale, *Z. Krist.*, 1936, **25**, 471). The present investigation gives the results of space group determination of the crystals of melamine which belongs to the cyanuric series of compounds.

Melamine has been studied crystallographically and the crystals have been found to develop the following faces:—

$$c(001); \quad m(110); \quad q(011); \quad m'(\bar{1}10); \quad \text{and} \quad q(0\bar{1}\bar{1}).$$

The crystals belong to the monoclinic prismatic class. The axial ratio is $a : b : c = 1.4091 : 1 : 0.9783$ and $111^\circ - 47'$ (Groth, "Chemische Kristallographie", p. 564-65).

The crystals of melamine were obtained from water. It was found that generally crystals had curved faces and only a few well developed crystals were obtained. These had developed $c(001)$, $m(110)$ and $m'(110)$ faces, which were identified by measuring the interfacial angles and further confirmed by taking several Laue photographs.

The dimensions of the unit cell calculated from the rotation photographs (Plates, I, II and III) are

$$a = 10.52\text{\AA}; \quad b = 7.44\text{\AA}; \quad c = 7.33\text{\AA}.$$

These give the axial ratio $a : b : c = 1.414 : 1 : 0.9851$, which agrees closely with Groth's ratio.

Tables I and II give the list of planes observed in the crystal along with their approximate relative intensities as estimated by the eye.

From Table I, it will be seen that (h0l) planes are halved when h is odd and (0lo) is also halved. The above halvings assign to the crystal of melamine the space group C_{2h}^2 . The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the cell and specific gravity of the crystals (found to be 1.57) is 4 (accurately 3.997).

TABLE I.

Prism planes.

Axial planes		(hol).		(okl).		(hko).	
001	v.s.	201	v.	011	v.s.	110	s.
002	s.	201	v.s.	012	w.	120	s
003	w.m.	202	s.	013	v.w.	130	w.m.
020	v.w.	202	v.s.	021	m.s.	210	v.s.
200	m.s.	203	s.	022	s.	230	m.
300	w.	204	v.w.	031	v.s.	240	m.
400	m.s.	401	s.	032	m.	310	v.s.
		402	s.	033	m.s.	320	s.
				042	m.s.	330	m.s.
						410	m.
						420	w.m.

TABLE II.

Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.	Plane.	Intensity.
111	v.s.	211	v.s.	311	w.	411	m.
111	s.	211	m.	311	m.	411	m.
112	s.	212	w.	312	m.s.	412	m.s.
112	m.	212	w.	313	m.s.	412	m.
121	m.s.	213	w.	314	v.w.	413	m.s.
121	v.s.	214	w.m.	321	m.	421	m.s.
122	m.	221	v.w.	321	m.s.	421	m.s.
123	w.	222	v.w.	322	w.m.	422	m.
123	w.m.	222	v.w.	322	w.m.	431	w.
131	v.s.	231	w.	323	m.	511	m.
132	m.s.	231	v.w.	331	m.	513	m.s.
132	m.	232	v.w.	332	v.s.	521	v.w.
133	m.	241	w.m.	333	w.m.		
		242	m.	341	m.		

Rotation photograph of melamine

Plate I.

a -axis

Plate II.

b -axis

Plate III.

c -axis

